

Constitutional Safeguards and the Pursuit of Gender Justice in India

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Abstract:

The concept of gender justice is an essential component of India's constitutional philosophy, rooted in the ideals of equality, liberty, and dignity enshrined in the Preamble and Fundamental Rights. The Indian Constitution lays a robust framework for promoting gender equality through various provisions, including Articles 14, 15, and 16, which prohibit discrimination and guarantee equal opportunities irrespective of gender. Additionally, Directive Principles of State Policy and Fundamental Duties further reinforce the commitment to achieving substantive equality between men and women. Over the years, the judiciary has played a transformative role in interpreting constitutional guarantees to expand the scope of gender justice, addressing issues such as workplace discrimination, reproductive rights, domestic violence, and representation in public life. However, despite these legal safeguards, the persistent challenges of patriarchy, socio-economic inequality, and gender-based violence continue to hinder the realization of true gender justice. This paper critically examines the constitutional provisions, legislative measures, and judicial pronouncements that shape India's gender justice framework while evaluating the gaps between constitutional ideals and social realities.

Keywords: Gender Justice, Constitutional Safeguards, Equality, Fundamental Rights, Women's Empowerment, Judicial Interpretation, Human Rights, India.

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Introduction

For a long time, women have been struggling to demolish gender bias and patriarchal supremacy. They have been trying hard to create a space for themselves in professional as well as domestic parapet. The tussle to overcome the conventional social assumption has not been easy at all. Time to time, efforts have taken place through women's movements to provide women their right place as men on the basis of equality.

Gender Justice and Constitutional Provisions

The Constitution is a public document. A special legal sanctity is attached with this. It determines the domain and legal framework of the government. For a long time, gender related issues were not in the focal point of the Government. After the independence of India, at the time of the promulgation of the Constitution of India, the Constitution makers were aware of the problems faced by women in society. Due to their sensitivity, gender specific provisions were inserted in the Constitution streaming other welfare laws for women. The supreme law of the land ensures equality and fair treatment to women. Not only this, it allows the government to bend the principle of equality in favour of women and children for their welfare.

- **Preamble**

The Preamble guides and directs the Constitution. It provides aims and objectives to the Constitution. It carries the fundamentals of the Constitution. The preamble flags the ideas and faith of the people of this country. The Preamble puts great emphasis on the principle of equality. The status of equality is the part of the basic structure of the Constitution. Even the Legislature cannot encroach upon the doctrine of basic structure by making a law. In any way in any form the basic structure of the Constitution remains intact.

In freedom struggle, women participated with great zeal and valor. The Constitution supports women for equal participation of women in administration as men. However, such participation is negligible in the country. Their participation in Indian politics is minimal. Such a situation has led to the demand for reservation of 33 percent seats for women in the Lok Sabha and Vidhan Sabha. Political empowerment of women has been brought by the Constitution (73rd Amendment) Act, 1992 and the Constitution (74th Amendment) Act, 1992 which reserves seat for women in Gram Panchayats and Municipal Bodies. There are several factors which push women back as illiteracy, lack of political awareness, domestic violence, and social odds and financial dependency.¹

There are several legislations providing equal economic rights to women in terms of working condition, wages, maternity benefits, equal remuneration, property rights, succession etc. These legislations work under the directions of fundamental rights and Directive Principles of State Policy. To provide equal status of equality to women in social parlance, personal laws are codified. To deal with crime against women in and out, criminal law and procedure are there to help the victim in case of any violence against her. To protect women from sexual harassment at her workplace, Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act, 2013 has been constituted. It aims to provide safe and secure environment to women at her workplace.

- **Fundamental Rights**

Human rights or fundamental rights protects an individual against the excess of the State. The idea of fundamental rights guards the individual from domination and injustice. Fundamental rights must be safeguarded all times against encroachment. Article 12 to 35 of the Constitution deals with fundamental rights of the people.

The Constitution of India promises the right to equality to people through Article 14 to 18. Equality is a vital limb of Indian democracy. The doctrine of equality before law is a necessary part of Rule

of Law which pervades the Indian Constitution. The underlying objectives behind Article 14 is to secure to all persons, citizens or non-citizens, the equality of status and opportunity referred to in the Preamble to our Constitution. This right embodies the idea of non-discrimination. In view of a certain amount of indefiniteness attached to the general principle of equality enunciated in Article 14, separate provisions to cover specific discriminatory situations have been made by subsequent Articles.² Article 15 prohibits discrimination against the citizens on the ground as religion, race, caste, sex or place of birth. Article 15(3) states that the State is empowered to make any special provision for women and children. Thus, one Article prohibits gender bias and another Article allows the State to positively discriminate to uplift the political, social and economic condition of women.

Article 16 of the Constitution promises equality of opportunity to all citizens "in matters relating to employment" or appointment to any office" under the State. As per Article 16(2), no citizen can be discriminated against, or be ineligible for any employment or office under the State, on the grounds only of religion, race, cast, sex, descent, place of birth or residence or any of them. Following the rule of equality in public employment is a being feature of our Constitution and the rule of law is its core, the Court cannot ignore itself from making an order inconsistent with Article 14 and 16 of the Constitution. Public employment is a facet of right equality provided under Article 16 of the Constitution.³ Thus, it is clear that the Constitution provides equal opportunity to women to work and get employed.

In **Dimple Singla v. Union of India**⁴, the Court expressed the concerned on the matter that there is a need to change the attitude of the society to eliminate discrimination against women. Still there is a doubt in the mind of society regarding the capacity of women to work. Still there is a gap between the fulfilments of fundamental rights of women.

In **C.B. Muthamma v. Union of India**⁵, a writ petition was filed by the Ms. Muthamma, employed in the Indian Foreign Services. She jolted against the denial of promotion in the current job. Not only this, she also highlighted against the bias persisting in Rule 18 of the Indian Foreign Service (Recruitment, Cadre, Seniority and Promotion) Rules, 1961. On this point, the Supreme Court mentioned that a service rule requiring a female employee to get written permission of the government authority before the commencement of her marriage and exclusion of her right to be appointed on the ground that she was a married women was discriminatory undoubtedly.

In another important case, the Supreme Court dealt with the bias provision of retirement on the marriage or pregnancy against the women employee in **Air India v. Nergesh Meerza**⁶. In this case, the validity of the regulation under which the Air hostess could be retired at the age of 35 years or if they got married within four years of their service or on the first pregnancy on the ground that they were discriminatory and infringes Article 14, 15 and 16 of the Constitution. The Court stated that a regulation providing for termination of service of an airhostess in Air India International on her first pregnancy has been considered unreasonable and a violation of her right. Such rule was found to be unacceptable in a civilized society. However, on the other hand, the court upheld the validity of the provision barring the air hostess to get married with four years of service as nothing is unreasonable and arbitrary in this provision.

Right to marry a person of choice is a fundamental right of a women and she cannot be forced to marry or not marry a person. In **Ashok Kumar Todi v. Kishwar Jahan**⁷, the Supreme Court held that a major person has right to marry according to his or her choice under Article 19. No one has any right to interfere in someone's conjugal life.

Gender equality also includes the right to live with human dignity. Women has right to privacy to keep her life personal. In this regard, **Neera Mathur v. LIC**⁸ can be discussed. In this case court stated that right to privacy is significant to right to life and with human dignity. Without privacy, human dignity cannot be fulfilled. Right to be privacy is inherited in Article 21. The Supreme Court disapproved the LIC questionnaire for the female employee which demanded their personal information. It was violating the right to privacy of the woman.

In **Gautam Kundu v. State of W.B.**⁹, the Court stated that a request to blood test to disapprove paternity of a child in a maintenance suit was rejected. It was held that a child born to a married

woman is considered legitimate unless contrary is proved. This presumption can be demolished on the basis of evidence. Thus, blood test cannot be order by the court as a matter of course.

To fulfil the idea of gender justice, it is mandatory to provide right against exploitation to women. Article 23 of the Constitution provides right against exploitation to women. This right protects women and children from being trafficked and forced into bonded labour. This right is mandatory to protect them from any kind of mental. Physical and sexual exploitation. The Legislature also enacted the Suppression of Immoral Traffic in Women and Girls Act, 1956(SITA) with objective to abolish trafficking of women and children. It a heinous crime against humanity. This Act is popularly known as the Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act, 1956. There are also provisions in Indian Penal Code which deal with this social economic malady. In **Vishal Jeet v. Union of India**¹⁰, the Supreme Court directed the State government to take action to eradicate child prostitution.

In **National Legal Service Authority V. Union of India**¹¹, the Supreme Court dealt with the matter of transgender. The court highlighted the trauma and agony that transgender undergo. Further, the court stated that no recognition of the right of transgender community leads to denial of their rights entrusted under Article 14 and 21 of the Constitution. Bias on the basis of sexual orientation and gender is unjustified and unreasonable and impairs the concept of equality. Every human being has right to enjoy right to equality without any discrimination on the basis of sexual orientation and gender identity. In the this case, the court upheld the trans gender's right to "decide their self-identified gender". The court directed the Central and State Government to provide legal recognition of their gender identity such as male, female or as third gender. The court directed to the governments to take notice of the problems faced by them and work on welfare scheme for their better life.¹²

- **Directive Principles of the State Policy**

Article 36 to 51 deals with Directive Principles of State Policy contained in part IV of the Constitution. In present time, the government fulfills the role of a welfare State which work to promote growth and welfare of people. Directive principles lay down some socio-economic goals for the government to achieve. They are incorporated in the Constitution to ameliorate the socio-economic plight of the masses. They are fundamental in the governance of the country. Fundamental rights are provided to individuals whereas directive principles are related to social concept. However, fundamental rights are enforceable and justiciable but directive principles are not so. Directive Principles are more moral in practice than legal. Even then, they both together fulfil the conscience of the Constitution. The efforts of the Supreme Court in fulfilling the duty has silhouetted the harmony between the two.

These directive principles are important for uplifting the plight of women also. The following provisions are incorporated to ameliorate the welfare of women:

Article 39(a) requires the State to direct its policy towards securing equal right of men and women to adequate means of livelihood.

Article 39(d) obligates equal pay for equal work for both men and women.

Article 39(e) envisions to protect health and strength of workers and tender age of children and to ensure that they are not forced by economic necessity to enter unsuitable work to their age or strength.

Article 42 deals to provide just and human conditions of work. It obligates the State to make provision for securing just human conditions and for maternity relief.

Article 44 deals with uniform civil code. This provision requires the State to secure for the citizens a Uniform Civil Code throughout the territory of India. This directive can be well utilized to achieve gender justice. However, the State could not implement uniform civil code to govern civil society matters related marriage, succession, divorce, adoption etc. Its implementation has been a matter of debate and dispute. There is a lot of opposition behind the idea of uniform civil code. India is a diverse country with different religions, faith and cultures. People follow their personal laws and don't want any kind of interference in that.

In this regard, **Sarla Mudgal v. Union of India**¹³ can be discussed. The Supreme Court dealing with the case where the question was raised whether a Hindu husband married under Hindu Law, after conversion to Islam, without getting separated from the first marriage, could marry a second time. In this case, it was held by the Court that such a marriage was illegal and the husband could be prosecuted for bigamy under section 494 of Indian Penal Code. In this case, four petitions were combined which had the similar issues. In the present case, the court mentioned that a Hindu marriage continues to stand even after the fact that one of the marriage partner has converted to Islam. There is no automatic dissolution of Hindu marriage. It can be broken only by the decree of the divorce provided by the court of law on the ground of Section 13 of the Hindu Marriage Act. The second nuptial of Hindu after his conversion to Islam is void in terms of Section 494 of India Penal Code and the husband is liable to be prosecuted for bigamy.¹⁴ In this Kuldeep Singh J, urged for the need of uniform civil code to the Indian government.

In **Pragati Verghese v. Cyril George Varghese**¹⁵, the Bombay High Court struck down the Section 10 of the Divorce Act, 1869 under which a Christian wife had to prove adultery along with cruelty or desertion while seeking a divorce on the ground that it violates the fundamental right of a Christian woman to live with human dignity under Article 21 of the Constitution.

In **Danial Latif v. Union of India**¹⁶ the constitutionality of the Muslim Women (Protection of Rights on Divorce) Act, 1986. The Supreme Court upheld the validity of the Act and held that a Muslim divorced woman has right to maintenance even after *iddat* period under the Act. As per Section 3(1) a of the Act, it is responsibility of the husband to make reasonable and fair provisions for the divorced wife which clearly extends the *iddat* period.

In **Seema v. Ashwani Kumar**,¹⁷ the first step towards the uniform civil code can be noticed which made the registration of all marriage's compulsory. The Supreme Court mandated that irrespective of the religion all marriages should be registered. Such practice will help women fighting for their rights in marriage. It would help to prove the status of marriage in case an unethical person denies the solemnization of marriage with the victim.

- **Fundamental Duties**

Fundamental duties have been comprised in part IV-A of the Constitution. Article 51-A was inserted by 42nd Amendment Act, 1976. It casts several duties on the every citizens of India. Article 51(e) says, "to promote harmony and the spirit of common brotherhood amongst all the people of India transcending religious, linguistic and regional or sectional diversities, to renounce practices derogatory to the dignity of women."

- **Local Bodies**

Article 243-D and 243-T of the Indian Constitution envisions reservation of seats for women in panchayat and municipalities. The 73rd and 74th Amendments to the Indian Constitution took place in 1992 deals with reservation for women of seats in elections to panchayats and municipalities. Parts IX and IX-A were added to the Constitution by these amendments and they are known as the Panchayati Raj and Nagarpalika Amendments Acts with Articles 243, 243-A to 243-O and 243-P to 243-ZG.¹⁸

Global Commitments to Achieve Gender Justice

Since its inception, the United Nations has been contributing for the women development and focusing to emancipate her from all kinds of discrimination and exploitation. It envisions women's economic and political participation. It aims to end violence against women at global level. It works on peace, humanity, coherence and gender equality. In this mission, the UN thrives to gain faith and support of the State governments. The Preamble of Universal Declaration of Human Right promotes equal rights for men and women, "United Nations in the Charter reaffirmed their faith in fundamental human rights, in the dignity and worth of the human person and in the equal rights of men and women and have determined to promote social progress and better standards of life in larger freedom."¹⁹

The United Nations Commission for the welfare of women in its 25th Report had suggested to the all-member States to establish a body or Commission to review and recommend measures to enhance equality between men and women in society. Following this resolution Government of India has set up

a Commission in 1971 on the Status of women. The Committee submitted its comprehensive report in 1974 with several recommendations. To fairly handle gender related issues, the Committee suggested an autonomous body at the Centre and the States. Consequently, the National Commission for Women Act, 1990 was passed. It took 16 years to establish National Commission for Women in India.²⁰

The Following landmarks are significant in this regards:

1. Establishment of the Commission on the Status of Women in 1946 to promote women's political, economic and social rights.
2. Adoption of the Convention for the Suppression of the Traffic in Persons and of the Exploitation of the Prostitution of Others by the General Assembly in 1949.
3. Adoption of the Convention Concerning Equal Remuneration for Men and Women Workers for Work of Equal Value by the ILO in 1951.
4. Adoption of the Convention on the Political Rights of women, including the right to vote by the general Assembly in 1952.
5. Adoption of the Convention on the Nationality of Married Women in 1957.
6. Adoption of the Convention Concerning Discrimination in respect to Employment and Occupation in 1960.
7. Convention on Consent to Marriage, Minimum Age for Marriage and Registration of Marriages, adopted by General Assembly in 1962.
8. Declaration on the Elimination of Discrimination Against Women adopted in 1967.
9. Adoption of the First World Plan of Action and Proclamation of the First World's UN Decade for Women: Equality, Development and Peace (1975-1985) by the World Conference of women in Mexico City in 1975.
10. International Research and Training Institute for the Advancement of Women (INSTRAW) by the general Assembly in 1976.
11. Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women, popularly known as (CEDAW) in 1979.
12. Second World Conference on women in Copenhagen in 1980.
13. Third World Conference on Women at Nairobi in 1985.
14. The first World Survey on the Role of Women in Development published in 1986.
15. The Declaration on the Elimination of Violence against Women adopted in 1993 by the general Assembly.
16. The Fourth World Conference on Women held in Beijing in 1995.
17. Declaration of the International Year for the empowerment of Women in 2001.

Conclusion and Suggestions

Gender equality is a basic aspect of fundamental rights. To ensure gender equality and gender justice, legislative framework is mandatory. Moreover, the protection envisioned and obligated by the Constitution on the government plays a vital role in gender related matters. The Constitution makes its intention very clear against the gender discrimination and exploitation in any form. In this regard, fundamental rights and directive principles have significant role to play together. To achieve the idea of gender equality and justice, it is mandatory to educate women. It is required her to be independent and in such women emancipation, society's role is fundamental. The change begins with home which is the primary level of society. There is a need of collective efforts of family, society and media to bring a change in the impoverished plight of women. In this process, it is the foremost responsibility of the Legislature, Executive and Judiciary to extent protect to Women whenever need arises.

References:

- ¹ Mamta Rao, Law Relation to Women and Children (EBC, 4th Ed., 2018).
- ² M.P. Jain, Indian Constitutional Law, 877 (Lexis Nexis, 7th ed, 2016).
- ³ Ibid
- ⁴ (2002) 2 SLJ 161
- ⁵ (1979) 4 SCC260

- 6 (1981) 4 SCC 335
7 (2011) 3 SCC 758
8 (1992) 1 SCC 286
9 (1993) 3 SCC 418
10 AIR 1990 SC 1412
11 (2014) 5SCC438
12 Indiakanoon.org, <https://indiankanoon.org/doc/193543132/> (last visited Jan 09, 2022)
13 (1995) 3 SCC 635
14 J.N. Pandey, Constitutional Law of India, 452 (Central Law Agency, 53ed., 2016).
15 AIR 1997 Bom.349
16 AIR 2001 SC3262
17 AIR 2006 SC1158
18 Mamta Rao, Law Relation to Women and Children (EBC, 4th Ed., 2018).
19 United Nations, <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/universal-declaration-of-human-rights> (last visited Jan 09, 2021).
20 Mamta Rao, Law Relation to Women and Children (EBC, 4th Ed., 2018).

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